

HIPPARCOS

Sensitivity of astrometric parameters to systematic abscissa errors

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1. Introduction

This note describes the astrometric effects of systematic observation errors of the form

$$\Delta w = \text{poly}(t) + \text{harm}(w) \quad (1)$$

i.e. the sum of a polynomial in time (t) and a harmonic series in the angle w (sun-related abscissa) defined in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Definition of w

The form (1) is of interest because poly(t) could represent a constant or slowly varying chromaticity, while harm(w) could be abscissa errors produced by periodic variations of the basic angle (γ). According to my note of 81-08-05, systematic variations by

$$\Delta \gamma = \sum_k [a_k \cos(kv) + b_k \sin(kv)] \quad (2)$$

where v is the solar azimuth (angle Sun-z-x) will cause abscissa errors by

$$\Delta w = \sum_k \frac{1}{2\sin(k\gamma/2)} [b_k \cos(kw) - a_k \sin(kw)] \quad (3)$$

The amplification factor in (3) is, for $\gamma = 58^{\circ}00$,

k	$[2\sin(k\gamma/2)]^{-1}$
1	1.03
2	0.59
3	0.50
4	0.56
5	0.87
6	4.78
7	-1.28
8	-0.63
:	:

2. Method

For each great-circle scan across a star, we have a deterministic observation equation of the form

$$h_1 \Delta\lambda \cos \beta + h_2 \mu_\lambda \cos \beta + h_3 \Delta\beta + h_4 \mu_\beta + h_5 \Pi = \Delta w(t, w) \quad (4)$$

$\Leftrightarrow$

$$\sum_i h_i p_i = d \quad (4')$$

where the h_i and w are computable in terms of the star's position (λ, β) , the position of the z axis (λ_z, β_z) , and time from mid-mission $t - t_0$. In matrix notations the assembly of observation equations is $\underline{H}\underline{p} = \underline{d}$, with LS solution

$$\hat{\underline{p}} = (\underline{H}'\underline{H})^{-1} \underline{H}'\underline{d} \quad (5)$$

The coefficients of improvement are the diagonal elements of $(\underline{H}'\underline{H})^{-1}$:

$$C_i \equiv [(\underline{H}'\underline{H})^{-1}]_{ii} \quad (6)$$

while the solutions $\hat{p}_i$ give the biases of the astrometric parameters for the assumed $\Delta w(t, w)$.

C_i and $\hat{p}_i$ were computed for 320 "stars" distributed fairly uniformly over the whole sky (Fig. 2). Uniform scanning with $\xi = 43^\circ$, $K = 6.4$, $T = 2.5$ yr and $FOV = 0.9^\circ$ was assumed, with no allowance for occultations.

3. Results

3.1. Coefficients of improvement

The average C_i for the whole sky (all stars) were:

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= 0.195 \quad (\Delta\lambda \cos \beta) & C_3 &= 0.157 \quad (\Delta\beta) & C_5 &= 0.240 \quad (\text{II}) \\ C_2 &= 0.272 \quad (\mu_\lambda \cos \beta) & C_4 &= 0.225 \quad (\mu_\beta) & & \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Individual C_i are plotted in Figs. 3a-e versus ecliptical latitude (β).

3.2. Constant and varying chromaticity

With the centred and normalized time argument $\tau \equiv 2(t - t_0)/T \in [-1, 1]$, the following Legendre polynomials were tried:

$$\text{poly}(t) = \begin{cases} L_0 \equiv 1 \\ L_1 \equiv \sqrt{3} \tau \\ L_2 \equiv \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{5} (3\tau^2 - 1) \\ L_3 \equiv \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{7} (5\tau^3 - 3\tau) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

These are orthonormal, i.e. $(L_k)_{\text{rms}} = 1$ and $\langle L_k L_j \rangle = 0$ for $k \neq j$. Resulting rms values of the biases $\hat{p}_i$ are given in the table below.

Variation	$(\hat{p}_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_2)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_3)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_4)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_5)_{\text{rms}}$
L_0	0.387	0.119	0.047	0.073	0.079
L_1	0.333	0.225	0.356	0.211	0.108
L_2	0.360	0.530	0.526	0.342	0.160
L_3	0.284	0.485	0.390	0.734	0.127
C_i	0.195	0.272	0.157	0.225	0.240

The values $(\hat{p}_i)_{\text{rms}}$ must always be compared with the coefficients of improvement C_i , since we will get $(\hat{p}_i)_{\text{rms}} = C_i$ in the case of independent, random abscissa errors with unit variance. The comparison is facilitated by defining the sensitivity S_i of the i :th astrometric parameter w.r.t. the variation $\Delta w(t, w)$ as

$$S_i \equiv (\hat{p}_i)_{\text{rms}} / C_i \quad (\text{see Appendix}) \quad (9)$$

$S_i < 1$ means that the systematic errors tend to cancel; $S_i > 1$ means that the astrometric parameter is sensitive to this particular kind of error.

3.3. Periodic abscissa errors

Putting

$$\text{harm}(w) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \cos(kw) & (\text{"even" variation}) \\ \sqrt{2} \sin(kw) & (\text{"odd" variation}) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

for $k = 1$ to 6, we obtain the results in the table below. Since the harmonic functions are also orthonormal (w.r.t. a uniform distribution of w), the results should again be compared with the coefficients of improvement C_i .

k	$(\hat{p}_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_2)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_3)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_4)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\hat{p}_5)_{\text{rms}}$
<u>even harmonics:</u> $\Delta w = \sqrt{2} \cos(kw)$					
1	0.789	0.266	0.216	0.401	0.187
2	0.220	0.410	0.290	0.331	0.207
3	0.546	0.302	0.215	0.341	0.173
4	0.241	0.987	0.195	0.281	0.306
5	0.500	0.425	0.165	0.376	0.216
6	0.302	0.661	0.157	0.247	0.450
<u>odd harmonics:</u> $\Delta w = \sqrt{2} \sin(kw)$					
1	0.015	0.003	0.005	0.002	2.073
2	0.129	0.469	0.516	0.159	0.257
3	0.193	0.380	0.248	0.402	0.519
4	0.169	0.331	0.403	0.360	0.173
5	0.230	0.408	0.273	0.603	0.426
6	0.224	0.389	0.440	0.499	0.284

AppendixSensitivity S_i [eqn (9)] for the various kinds of abscissa errors.

Variation Δw	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_4	S_5
$L_0(\tau)$	1.98	0.44	0.30	0.32	0.33
$L_1(\tau)$	1.71	0.83	2.27	0.94	0.45
$L_2(\tau)$	1.85	1.95	3.35	1.52	0.67
$L_3(\tau)$	1.46	1.78	2.48	3.26	0.53
$\sqrt{2} \cos(w)$	4.05	1.36	1.38	1.78	0.78
$\sqrt{2} \cos(2w)$	1.13	1.51	1.85	1.47	0.86
$\sqrt{2} \cos(3w)$	2.80	1.11	1.37	1.52	0.72
$\sqrt{2} \cos(4w)$	1.24	3.63	1.24	1.25	1.28
$\sqrt{2} \cos(5w)$	2.56	1.56	1.05	1.67	0.90
$\sqrt{2} \cos(6w)$	1.55	2.43	1.00	1.10	1.88
$\sqrt{2} \sin(w)$	0.08	0.01	0.03	0.01	8.64
$\sqrt{2} \sin(2w)$	0.66	1.72	3.29	0.71	1.07
$\sqrt{2} \sin(3w)$	0.99	1.40	1.58	1.79	2.16
$\sqrt{2} \sin(4w)$	0.87	1.22	2.57	1.60	0.72
$\sqrt{2} \sin(5w)$	1.18	1.50	1.74	2.68	1.78
$\sqrt{2} \sin(6w)$	1.15	1.43	2.80	2.22	1.18

DISTRIBUTION OF 320 TEST POINTS ON THE SKY

FIG. 2

Coefficient of improvement (C_1 , for $\Delta\lambda \cos \beta$) versus ecliptical latitude (β) for the 320 test points. Assumptions:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= 43.00^\circ \\ K &= 6.40 \\ R &= 12 \\ \phi &= 0.9^\circ \\ T &= 2.5 \text{ yr} \end{aligned}$$

FIG. 3A

FIG. 3B

FIG. 3C

FIG. 3D

FIG. 3E